

Revision of the land Mollusca (Gastropoda) of the Arquipélago das Berlengas (Portugal) with new records and notes on the affinities of the endemic *Oestophora barrelsi* Hovestadt & Ripken, 2015 (Trissexodontidae)

Revisión de los moluscos terrestres (Gastropoda) del Arquipélago das Berlengas (Portugal) con nuevos registros y notas sobre las afinidades del endemismo *Oestophora barrelsi* Hovestadt & Ripken, 2015 (Trissexodontidae)

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Recibido el 8-XII-2020. Aceptado el 12-VI-2021

ABSTRACT

An annotated list is presented of the species of land Mollusca of the Arquipélago das Berlengas off the west coast of Portugal, based on new fieldwork and critical reviews of museum specimens and literature. For Berlenga Grande we accept records of 14 species (discounting *Cornu aspersum*), two of which are newly reported here (*Truncatellina calli-cratis*, *Vitrea contracta*). The only other island on which land snails are known is Farilhão Grande, with three species confirmed, all of which are also known from Berlenga Grande. Of these, *Oestophora barrelsi* is an endemic species occurring on both islands; new data on its DNA sequences and genital anatomy demonstrate a close relationship to *O. barbula* and *O. barbella*. Whether taxonomic separation is appropriate for different shell morphotypes of *Xeroplexa olisippensis* s.l. on each island is still to be decided by ongoing research. All records of nine other species are dismissed as due to misidentifications.

RESUMO

É apresentada uma lista anotada das espécies de Moluscos terrestres do Arquipélago das Berlengas, situado ao largo da costa ocidental portuguesa. Esta é baseada em novo trabalho de campo e revisões da literatura e de exemplares de museu. Para a Berlenga Grande são aceites registos de catorze espécies (sem considerar

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Cornu aspersum), duas das quais são aqui reportadas como novas (*Truncatellina callicratis*, *Vitrea contracta*). A única outra ilha do arquipélago de onde se conhecem moluscos terrestres é o Farilhão Grande, com três espécies confirmadas, todas também conhecidas da Berlenga Grande. Destas, *Oestophora barreisi* é uma espécie endêmica que ocorre em ambas as ilhas; novos dados sobre as sequências de ADN e anatomia genital, demonstram uma relação estreita com *O. barbula* e *O. barbella*. A adequação de tratamento taxonômico separado de diferentes morfotipos de *Xeroplexa olisippensis* s.l. de cada ilha está ainda por decidir, tendo em conta investigação em curso. Todos os registos de nove outras espécies são descartados, dado corresponderem a identificações erróneas.

RESUMEN

Se presenta una lista comentada de las especies de moluscos terrestres del Arquipélago das Berlengas, ubicado frente a la costa oeste de Portugal.

Este listado se basa en nuevos trabajos de campo y en revisiones de las publicaciones realizadas y de ejemplares depositados en museos. Para Berlenga Grande, se aceptan registros de catorce especies (sin considerar *Cornu aspersum*), dos de las cuales se reportan aquí como nuevas (*Truncatellina callicratis*, *Vitrea contracta*). La única otra isla del archipiélago de la que se conocen moluscos terrestres es Farilhão Grande, con tres especies confirmadas, todas también conocidas de Berlenga Grande. De estos, *Oestophora barreisi* es una especie endémica que se encuentra en ambas islas; nuevos datos sobre sus secuencias de ADN y anatomía genital demuestran una relación estrecha con *O. barbula* y *O. barbella*. La separación taxonómica de dos morfotipos diferentes de *Xeroplexa olisippensis* s.l. de estas dos islas no se ha decidido todavía, estando pendiente de investigaciones en curso. Todos los registros de otras nueve especies se descartan, ya que corresponden a identificaciones erróneas.

KEY WORDS: check list, island faunas, faunal changes, endemic species, misidentifications, voucher specimens, *Oestophora* genital anatomy & DNA sequences.

PALAVRAS-CHAVE: lista, faunas insulares, alterações de fauna, espécies endêmicas, identificações erróneas, exemplares-testemunho, anatomia genital & sequências de ADN de *Oestophora*.

PALABRAS CLAVE: listado, fauna insular, cambios en la fauna, especies endémicas, identificaciones erróneas, ejemplares de referencia anatomía genital y secuencias de ADN de *Oestophora*.

INTRODUCTION

This list provides a critical compilation of the species of land Mollusca (Gastropoda) of the Arquipélago das Berlengas, located off western mainland Portugal in the Atlantic Ocean (Fig. 1). The largest island, Berlenga Grande (39°24'52"N., 9°30'22"W.) lies 10.4 km offshore from western Portugal (Cabo Carvoeiro), with a land area of 0.788 km² formed of granitic rock, its highest point being 150 m above sea-level. The only other island known to support land snails is the much smaller Farilhão Grande (39°28'43"N., 9°32'40"W.) located 17.4 km from Cabo Carvoeiro, with land area of <0.04 km² formed of

gneiss bedrock, its highest point being 34 m above sea-level. Berlenga Grande has mainly open vegetation of herbs and grasses; Farilhão Grande has a much smaller flora, mainly of low halophytes. Berlenga Grande has a long history of human occupation, and it still supports a number of small houses, a large historic fort and a lighthouse, whereas Farilhão Grande is a rather inhospitable steep rocky islet on which a lighthouse is the only building. The terrestrial ecology of both islands is influenced by large colonies of Yellow-legged Gull *Larus michahellis* and other seabirds. The whole Arquipélago is pro-

Figure 1. Maps showing the location of the Arquipélago das Berlengas (Portugal) and details of the islands of Farilhão Grande (map 1) and Berlenga Grande (map 2). Letters mark locations mentioned in the text: on Farilhão Grande, the Farol is at C; on Berlenga Grande, the site with *Truncatellina callicratis* is at B, the Farol at D, the Fortaleza at E, Pedra Negra at F, the Cisterna at G, and the Harbour at H.

*Figura 1. Mapas que muestran la ubicación del Arquipélago das Berlengas (Portugal) y detalles de las islas de Farilhão Grande (mapa 1) y Berlenga Grande (mapa 2). Las letras marcan los lugares mencionados en el texto: en Farilhão Grande, el Farol se marca con C; en Berlenga Grande, el sitio con *Truncatellina callicratis* se marca con B, el Farol con D, la Fortaleza con E, Pedra Negra con F, la Cisterna con G y el Puerto con H.*

tected and managed by the Portuguese authorities as the Reserva Natural das Berlengas, forming part of the World Network of Biosphere Reserves. Berlenga Grande receives many visiting tourists.

GIRARD (in DAVEAU, 1884) reported early records for six land snail species collected in 1883 by Jules Daveau, comprising two from Farilhão Grande and five from Berlenga (= Berlenga Grande). FISCHER (1884), reporting on the same collection, did not add any new information. Girard's specimens were probably lost in the fire at the Museu Zoológico de Lisboa in 1978. NOBRE (in NOBRE & BRAGA, 1942) also published

lists of the snail faunas of each island. MATOS (2002) provided a detailed review of older literature on the land Mollusca and added additional records from her own visits involving collection of numerous specimens in 1994 and 1996. The taxonomy adopted followed a checklist published soon afterwards (MATOS, 2004), but taxonomy and some of the identifications from the islands were superseded by the undated book published privately by MATOS [2014]. Shells of *Oestophora* collected on Berlenga Grande by Adriaan Hovestadt in 1989 were eventually named as an endemic species *O. barrelsi* by HOVESTADT & RIPKEN (2015).

The present list attempts to record the current state of knowledge of the fauna, remove erroneous and dubious records, and comment on taxonomic, nomenclatural and distributional problems that need to be addressed. In addition, the genital anatomy and DNA sequence data for *Oestophora barrelsi* are described for the first time, allowing discussion of its affinities.

METHODS

Land-snail shells and specimens in spirit including *Xeroplexa* species were collected at both islands over the past decade by GC; RMM also obtained shells. Further visits to both islands were organised to survey and collect non-marine Mollusca as follows: Farilhão Grande (16 May 2018, GC, DTH, GAH, JMS); Berlenga Grande (26 July 2018, ACAS, GC, DTH, GAH, RMM; 24 Aug. 2019, GC, DTH, RMM). On these visits all likely habitats were searched and specimens were collected of all land snails found. The second visit to Berlenga Grande concentrated on detailed sampling and field-sieving around 29SMD 56383 62972 (Fig. 1, location B), close to the place where a *Truncatellina* shell had been found on the previous visit. The habitat here was a dry open slope above a coastal inlet, with some exposed granite, loose humic soil, and patchy vegetation of grasses and herbs. Patches of dead *Carpobrotus edulis* were present close by, these having been killed with herbicide as part of management work to control this invasive alien plant. Sampling here used nested 2.0 and 0.5 mm sieves to obtain “fines” which were sorted later using a stereo-microscope, as well as removal of whole samples of surface soil.

The only coastal pulmonate previously recorded (*Onchidella celtica*) is included here. Coastal Ellobiidae were sought by us in several places but not found, although they seem likely to be present somewhere despite the steepness of the rocky coasts. No terrestrial slugs (other than the coastal *Onchidella*)

and no freshwater molluscs are known from the Arquipélago.

Following our own fieldwork and a review of older literature, DTH and RMM visited the Museu da Ciência, Universidade de Coimbra on 19 Dec. 2019 to study the rich collections from the Arquipélago housed there in the Collection of the late Dra Rolanda Maria Albuquerque de Matos.

The taxonomy and nomenclature adopted follow HOLYOAK, HOLYOAK & MENDES (2019). A list of taxa reported from the Arquipélago das Berlengas for which all records appear to be erroneous or at best unsubstantiated is also given at the end of the main systematic list.

The following account describes the methodology used for genetic analyses of *Oestophora* species: Total genomic DNA was extracted from foot tissue using the DNeasy Blood and Tissue kit (Qiagen, Valencia, CA, USA) according to the manufacturer’s instructions. Two mitochondrial gene fragments (*COI* and 16S rRNA) and a nuclear gene cluster (ITS1-5.8S rRNA-ITS2-28S rRNA) were selected for molecular analyses. General PCR cycling conditions used for DNA amplification were 1 min at 96 °C, 35 cycles (30 s at 96 °C, 30 s at 55 °C, 1 min at 72 °C) and 72 °C for 10 min. PCR products were purified and sequenced at MacroGen Inc. using ABI3730XL or ABI3700 sequencers (see Tables I and II for GenBank accession numbers and primer pairs). We also downloaded other *Oestophora* sequences available from GenBank, as well as several sequences from the family Trissexondontidae which were included as outgroups. Sequences were aligned with MAFFT v.7 online version (KATO, ROZEWICKI & YAMADA, 2019), using the Q-INS-I algorithm for the 16SrRNA and 5.8S-ITS2-28S gene fragments and the ‘auto’ strategy for the *COI*. For phylogenetic reconstruction, both Bayesian inference and maximum-likelihood methods were used, on the combined dataset partitioned by genes. The evolutionary model for each partition was estimated prior to analysis with PartitionFinder v.2.1.1 (LANFEAR ET AL., 2017)

Table I. Genbank accession numbers and locality data for *Oestophora* and other Trissexodontidae used for study of DNA sequences. *Tabla I. Números de registro en Genbank y datos de localidad de Oestophora y otros Trissexodontidae empleados para el estudio de las secuencias de ADN.*

Species	Voucher	COI	GenBank accession numbers 16S	ITS1	ITS2	Locality	Province	Country	UTM
<i>Oestophora tarmieri</i>		FJ786487.1	FJ786433.1	FJ786536.1	JQ805009.1	Cortes de la Frontera	Málaga	Spain	30STF84
<i>Oestophora silvae</i>	isolate_01	FJ786485.1	FJ786435.1	FJ786535.1	JQ805011.1	Arredondo	Cantabria	Spain	30TWN58
<i>Oestophora silvae</i>	isolate_02	FJ786486.1	FJ786436.1	FJ786534.1	JQ805012.1	Pugasari	Bizkaia	Spain	30TWN08
<i>Oestophora priebii</i>	isolate_01	FJ786481.1	FJ786428.1	FJ786530.1	JQ805005.1	Santo Tomé	Jaén	Spain	30SWH00
<i>Oestophora marinae</i>	isolate_01	FJ786479.1	FJ786432.1	FJ786528.1	JQ805006.1	Castriñ	Granada	Spain	30SWG28
<i>Oestophora ebraia</i>		FJ786483.1	FJ786430.1	FJ786532.1	JQ805010.1	Tolox	Málaga	Spain	30SUF26
<i>Oestophora orizii</i>		FJ786484.1	FJ786429.1	FJ786533.1	JQ805008.1	Cortes de la Frontera	Málaga	Spain	30STF84
<i>Oestophora calpeana</i>		FJ786478.1	FJ786427.1	FJ786527.1	JQ805004.1	Gibraltar	Gibraltar	Spain	30STF80
<i>Oestophora barbella</i> *	isolate_01	FJ786476.1	FJ786437.1	FJ786525.1	JQ805013.1	Vilches	Jaén	Spain	30SVH52
<i>Oestophora barbella</i>	P523.1	MW193963*	MW205199*	MW197706*	MW197710*	Barçola (nw. of Seritá)	Beira Baixa	Portugal	29SNE70
<i>Oestophora barbella</i>	P524.1	MW193964*	MW205200*	MW197707*	MW197711*	N. side of IÇB road at 2.4 km due W. of Avelar (centre)	Beira Litoral	Portugal	29SNE51
<i>Oestophora barreisi</i>	P455.1	MW193965*	MW205201*	MW197708*	MW197712*	central part of Farilhõe Grande island	Estremadura	Portugal	29SMD56
<i>Oestophora barreisi</i>	P471.1	No data	MW205202*	MW197709*	MW197713*	Berlenga island, head of small beach near landing	Estremadura	Portugal	29SMD56
Outgroups									
<i>Caracollina lenticula</i>		FJ786454.1	FJ786405.1	FJ786504.1	JQ805002.1	Valverde del Camino	Huelva	Spain	29SPB96
<i>Gasullia simplicula</i>		FJ786461.1	FJ786412.1	FJ786511.1	JQ805001.1	Tiarsis	Huelva	Spain	29SPB66
<i>Suboestophora gasulli</i>		FJ786459.1	FJ786410.1	FJ786510.1	JQ805000.1	Nerva	Huelva	Spain	9SQ817
<i>Suboestophora boscae</i>		FJ786490.1	FJ786445.1	FJ786539.1	JQ805016.1	Pego	Alicante	Spain	30SYI50
<i>Mastigophallus rangianus</i>		FJ786474.1	FJ786425.1	FJ786524.1	JQ805019.1	Port de la Selva	Girona	Spain	30TEG18
<i>Trissexodon constrictus</i>		FJ786497.1	FJ786449.1	FJ786547.1	JQ805017.1	Pugasari	Bizkaia	Spain	30TWN08
<i>Giffenbergia turriplana</i>	isolate_01	FJ786463.1	FJ786414.1	FJ786513.1	JQ805026.1	Tavira	Algarve	Portugal	29SPB10

Asterisks (*) indicate new sequences generated for this study.

Oestophora barbella isolate 01 was submitted to GenBank by GÓMEZ-MOJNER *ET AL.* (2013) as *O. barbella*. However, following the revision by HOLYOAK & HOLYOAK (2012a) we consider that this specimen should be reidentified as *O. barbella*.

Table II. List of primers used for DNA amplification and sequencing.
 Table II. Lista de cebadores usados para la amplificación y secuenciación del ADN.

Gene	Primer	Sequence	Reference
COI	LCO1490	5'-GGTCAACAAATCATAAAGATATTGG-3'	FOLMER <i>ET AL.</i> , 1994
	HCO2198	5'-TAAACTTCAGGGTGACCAAAAAATCA-3'	FOLMER <i>ET AL.</i> , 1994
16S rRNA	16Scs1	5'-AAACATACCTTTTGCATAATGG-3'	CHIBA, 1999
	16Scs2	5'-AGAAACTGACCTGGCTTACG-3'	CHIBA, 1999
ITS1	ITS1L-F	5'-TCCGTAGGTGAACCTGCGGAAGGAT-3'	HILLIS & DIXON 1991
	58C-R	5'-TGC GTTCAAGATATCGATGTTCAA-3'	HILLIS & DIXON 1991
5.8S-ITS2-28S	LSU-1	5'-CTAGCTGC GAGAATTAATGTGA-3'	WADE <i>ET AL.</i> , 2006
	LSU-3	5'-ACTTCCCTCACGGTACTTG-3'	WADE <i>ET AL.</i> , 2006

using the Bayesian information criterion to select among models (COI 1st TRN+I, COI 2nd F81+I, COI 3rd TVM+G, 16S rRNA GTR+G, ITS1 and ITS2 HKY+G and 5.8S and 28S rRNAs JC+I).

Bayesian inference analyses were conducted with MrBayes v.3.2.7 (RONQUIST *ET AL.*, 2012). Two independent runs were continued for 50×10⁶ generations saving trees each 1000 generations with the first 25% of trees being discarded as burn-in. Maximum likelihood analyses were carried out using RAxML v.8.2.12 (STAMATAKIS, 2014) under the GTRGAMMA model, with 1000 nonparametric bootstrap replicates to assess node support. Uncorrected pairwise *p*-distances were calculated with MEGA v. 1.10.8 (KUMAR *ET AL.*, 2018).

Abbreviations:

ACAS: Ana Catarina Ambrosina da Silva;
 BJGM: Prof. Benjamin Gómez Moliner;
 CGAH: Collection of G.A. & D.T. Holyoak;
 CRMM: Collection of Rui da Costa Mendes;
 IMS: 80% industrial methylated spirit;
 JMS: José Mendes Simões;
 MCUC: Museu da Ciência, Universidade de Coimbra, Portugal;
 MGRS: coordinates based on Military Grid Reference System;
 NMW.Z: National Museum of Wales, Cardiff, U.K.;

s.l.: *sensu lato* (in the wide sense);
s.s.: *sensu stricto* (in the narrow sense);
 sh: shell(s);
 spp.: species (plural).

SYSTEMATIC LIST OF SPECIES RECORDED IN THE ARQUIPÉLAGO DAS BERLENGAS

Family ONCHIDIIDAE

Onchidella celtica (Cuvier, 1816)

A supralittoral, coastal slug, previously reported from Berlengas by MACEDO, MACEDO & BORGES (1999: 374).

Family LAURIIDAE

Lauria cylindracea (Da Costa, 1778)

First recorded from Farilhão Grande and Berlenga Grande by NOBRE (in NOBRE & BRAGA, 1942: 12), who reported it as very common. We did not find it on Farilhão Grande, despite detailed searches and there are reasons to doubt Nobre's report (see Conclusions below). Both of our visits to Berlenga Grande recorded it in several places. It was abundant there in an area within 20 metres of 29SMD 56383 62972 (see above for habitat and other notes), with hundreds of shells in samples taken, where many including living individuals were found on 24 Aug. 2019 (CGAH, CRMM).

Family TRUNCATELLINIDAE

Truncatellina has been treated as part of the Vertiginidae in much of the recent literature (e.g. HOLYOAK *et al.*, 2019: 127) but it was placed as a separate family by BOUCHET *ET AL.* (2017: 364).

Truncatellina callicratis (Scacchi, 1833)

Newly recorded for Berlenga Grande on 26 July 2018 from a single shell found in a soil sample collected by RMM. Extensive sampling in the same area within 20 m of 29SMD 56383 62972 (see Fig. 1 for location and above for habitat and other notes) on 24 Aug. 2019 produced 372+ shells (CGAH, CRMM). Some of these shells were very fresh and the abundant material allowed confirmation that a form of *T. callicratis* developing three apertural teeth in the adult shells is involved.

HOLYOAK, HOLYOAK & TORRES ALBA (2012) reviewed records of the genus from mainland Portugal and Spain and found this to be much the commonest species. Populations with shells lacking apertural teeth predominate in the Algarve and S. Spain, whereas most (not all) of the populations further north develop up to three teeth.

Family OXYCHILIDAE

Oxychilus cellarius (O.F. Müller, 1774)

Recorded on Berlenga Grande at “encosta do Carreiro do Mosteiro” by NOBRE (in NOBRE & BRAGA, 1942: 11), but not encountered by MATOS (2002: 33). We found small numbers on both of our visits to this island (e.g. on 26 July 2018, 7 sh including 3 adults, largest 5 x 10 mm, CRMM). Although live animals have not been examined to check body coloration or genital anatomy, there is no indication that *Oxychilus draparnaudi* (H. Beck, 1837) is present.

Family PRISTOLOMATIDAE

Vitrea contracta (Westerlund, 1871)

Newly recorded on Berlenga Grande in 2018 and 2019, in the area within 20 m of 29SMD 56383 62972; see above for

notes on the habitat. Around 95 empty shells have been collected (in CGAH and CRMM), some of which were fresh.

Family GEOMITRIDAE

Cochlicella acuta (O.F. Müller, 1774)

First reported by NOBRE (in NOBRE & BRAGA, 1942: 12) from Berlenga Grande and Farilhão Grande (although the latter may be questionable: see Conclusions below). He used the name *Helix barbara* for it in error, which as pointed out by MATOS (2002: 33, 2014: 182), was often misused in this manner by early authors. The Matos Collection at MCUC includes three samples of correctly identified shells of *C. acuta* from the Arquipélago: one from Farilhão Grande (2019.1700321, 4 sh, Farilho Grande, Cima by Farol, 8 Aug. 1996), two from Berlenga Grande (2019.17.00305, Berlengas, Farol N, 18 June 1996, HF & RM; 00335, Berlenga, 6-8 June 1994, Helena Farrall). We did not find this species on either island, but the living snails may be immature and hence inconspicuous in late spring and summer.

Cochlicella conoidea (Draparnaud, 1801)

GIRARD (in DAVEAU, 1884: 447) reported it was numerous on Berlenga (= Berlenga Grande) based on collections by Jules Daveau. MATOS (2002: 34) reported 63 shells there from “zona do Farol” and “patió da Fortaleza”. We found living immature snails and dead adult shells on 16 July 2018 (in CGAH and CRMM).

Ponentina ponentina (Morelet, 1845)

The first record from Berlenga Grande was given as *Trichia occidentalis* (Recluz, 1845) by MATOS (2002: 34), who saw more than 200, about half of them living and published a photograph clearly showing the shell characters. We also found it to be common in 2018. MATOS (2014: 189) treated *P. ponentina* incorrectly as a synonym of *P. revelata* (Michaud, 1831). The taxonomy adopted for this genus here follows the review by HOLYOAK & HOLYOAK (2012b), which showed that *P. ponentina* is readily distinguishable from congeners using shell

characters. In addition to our own material, ten samples studied by us in the Matos Collection at MCUC were all confirmed as this species.

Xeroplexa olisippensis (Servain, 1880) *s.l.*

GIRARD (in DAVEAU, 1884: 446) reported *Helix intersecta* Poiret as widespread on Berlenga and Farilhão based on collections by Jules Daveau. NOBRE & BRAGA (1942: 35) listed the species for Berlenga. MATOS (2002: 35) treated this taxon as *Candidula intersecta* (Poiret, 1801), noting it as the most ubiquitous and common snail species on Farilhão Grande and Berlenga. We have confirmed that the Matos Collection at MCUC contains four samples of "*Candidula intersecta*" from Farilhão Grande (2019.17.00331, 00363, 00364, 00369) plus four representing the same taxon but labelled erroneously as "*Helicella cistorum*" (see below under latter heading). Her collection also contains no fewer than 33 samples labelled as "*Candidula intersecta*" or just "*Candidula*" from Berlenga, along with others bearing different names from the latter island that can in fact be referred to the same taxon (see also our accounts of *Candidula unifasciata*, *Helicella cistorum*, *H. conspurcata*).

GC collected live adults that he preserved in ethanol from both islands and passed these to DTH, who was able to confirm that they show characters of the distal genitalia matching those of *Candidula s.l.* (with a single large dart sac), but correspond to "*C. olisippensis* (Servain, 1880) in having a long penial flagellum rather than Portuguese and British "*C. intersecta*" which have a short flagellum (see HOLYOAK & HOLYOAK, 2014).

Soon afterwards our fieldwork on Farilhão Grande and Berlenga Grande confirmed that a "*Candidula*" species was very common on both islands and we obtained much larger samples of shells and of bodies for dissection. It became apparent that a distinctive shell morphotype occupies Farilhão Grande (Fig. 2 D-F), differing from all other Portuguese members of the genus in having a very large shell that retains a weak marginal keel even when adult (most

other congeners from Portugal have body whorl of adult shells rounded, except that in "*C. setubalensis* (L. Pfeiffer, 1850) and "*C. coudensis* (G. Holyoak & D. Holyoak, 2010) it has a sharp keel). The population on Berlenga Grande (Fig. 2 A-C) differs clearly from that of Farilhão, but it is not easily delimited by characters of the shell or genital anatomy from the Portuguese mainland species "*C. olisippensis*).

Preliminary sequencing studies of several mitochondrial DNA markers from Portuguese "*Candidula*" species were reported by MADEIRA ET AL. (2017). Their fig. 4 (p. 9) presented a cladogram showing that material from Berlengas and Farilhão (named therein as "*C. belemensis*", but based on some of the same specimens collected by GC that were dissected by DTH) each form a distinct clade, separate from other Portuguese species of the genus.

CHUECA ET AL. (2018: 366) found that the broadly conceived genus *Candidula* as used by HOLYOAK & HOLYOAK (2014) was polyphyletic, so they transferred *Candidula olisippensis* and most related species from Portugal to the genus *Xeroplexa*. They also found that populations from Galicia with a long flagellum form a separate clade more closely allied to *X. intersecta* than to *X. olisippensis*.

Ongoing studies of all Portuguese *Xeroplexa* by LJC and BJGM have incorporated the Farilhão Grande and Berlenga Grande material collected by GC. They have also developed additional mitochondrial markers and sequenced these on extensive material, improving statistical support for the resulting phylogenies. The new studies have revealed further complexity in the populations of *Xeroplexa olisippensis s.l.* occurring on the mainland of Portugal. Any taxonomic recognition of the two morphotypes from the Arquipélago das Berlengas is therefore premature without fuller understanding of the wide variability of its mainland populations.

Xerotricha apicina (Lamarck, 1822)

Recorded from Berlenga Grande as *Helix apicina* in large numbers by Gi-

Figure 2. Representative shells of adult specimens of *Xeroplexa olisippensis* s.l. (Geomitridae) from Arquipélago das Berlengas (Portugal). A-C: from Berlenga Grande, 26 July 2018, CGAH (P471), shell breadth 9.72 mm; D-F: from Farilhão Grande, 16 May 2018, CGAH (P455), shell breadth 13.10 mm.

Figura 2. Conchas representativas de exemplares adultos de *Xeroplexa olisippensis* s.l. (Geomitridae) de Arquipélago das Berlengas (Portugal). A-C: de Berlenga Grande, 26 julio 2018, CGAH (P471), ancho de la concha 9,72 mm; D-F: de Farilhão Grande, 16 mayo 2018, CGAH (P455), ancho de la concha 13,10 mm.

RARD (in DAVEAU, 1884: 446) based on collections by Jules Daveau. It was also listed by NOBRE & BRAGA (1942). MATOS (2002: 35) found it on the island only as six shells “nas traseiras do Farol da Berlenga”, and suggested it might be in the process of disappearing. The Matos Collection at MCUC contains one sample (2019.17.00382, “Berlenga Grande, Farol, 18 jun. 1996”) with six old shells in good condition. We did not find the species.

Family HELICIDAE

Cornu aspersum (O.F. Müller, 1774)

Recorded as *Helix aspersa* on Berlenga Grande by MATOS (2002: 36) on the basis of a single shell from the “pátios da Fortaleza”. She commented that Luis Burnay had reported a single living individual at the same locality which might have been the same individual, and that the species was undoubtedly an acciden-

tal introduction. It may have arrived there living as an item intended for human food, as with the next species. There is no evidence of the species having become established on the island.

Otala lactea lactea (O.F. Müller, 1774)

The Matos Collection at MCUC contains two single shells from Berlengas (= Berlenga Grande), “6/6/94 - HF Berlengas por tras do Farol” and “19 junho 1996 Berlengas, RM & HF”. Both are adult shells in good condition and correctly identified. MATOS (2014: 228) did not map or mention it for the Arquipélago. On 26 July 2018 three adult shells were collected (CRMM). The Ranger, Paulo Crisóstomo (pers. comm. to GC), reported that about 20 years ago the species did not occur on the island. Hence it is apparently a relatively modern introduction to the island, which possibly arrived as human food.

A revision of the genus by HOLYOAK & HOLYOAK (2017: 445-446) designated a neotype for the species (in NMW.Z) from N. of Porto Covo, Baixo Alentejo. The species is sometimes treated as polytypic. If subspecies are recognised, the neotype designation ensures that it is the nominate form which occurs in Portugal.

Theba pisana pisana (O.F. Müller, 1774)

Recorded from Berlenga Grande by GIRARD (in DAVEAU, 1884: 446), as widespread, based on collections by Jules Daveau. NOBRE (in NOBRE & BRAGA, 1942: 11) reported it as very common on Berlenga and occurring also on Farilhão Grande. Although MATOS (2014: 220) mapped it for Farilhão Grande (hectad 29SMD56) on the basis of Nobre's report, and suggested it might have become extinct there, we regard the record as questionable (see Conclusions below).

The form that remains plentiful on parts of Berlenga Grande is *T. p. pisana*, not *T. p. almogravensis* which is a localised endemic on sand dunes in south-western Portugal (HOLYOAK & HOLYOAK, 2016). *T. p. pisana* is widespread and often abundant over most of Portugal, except for most of the north-east of the country and large areas away from coasts elsewhere in the north. It is widely collected for food and hence often introduced by man deliberately, as well as accidentally with plants or attached to vehicles, building materials, etc., so it was perhaps introduced originally on Berlenga Grande. Although the nominate subspecies has become widespread near the coasts of western Europe, northwards to Ireland, Wales, England, Belgium and the Netherlands, it is apparently not known by reliable fossil records from most of Europe and hence it should not be uncritically assumed to have colonised widely by natural means.

Family HYGROMIIDAE

Portugala inchoata (Morelet, 1845)

Recorded from Berlenga Grande by GIRARD (in DAVEAU, 1884: 446-447), "apenas na vertente norte" based on

collections by Jules Daveau. Also listed from this island by NOBRE (in NOBRE & BRAGA (1942: 11) from "planalto da ilha". MATOS (2002: 34) recorded two completely white shells from "traseiras do Farol da Berlenga" and questioned whether it was a species introduced accidentally or in the process of disappearing. The Matos Collection at MCUC contains a single sample with two shells (2019.17.00349) from Berlengas, Farol, 18 June 1996. One is a good but old adult shell with a hole in it and clearly *Portugala inchoata*; the other is also a good adult shell, but it has a bigger umbilicus and is not *P. inchoata*, possibly a large *Cerneuella virgata*. It seems possible that both shells reached the island in the gut of gulls that had fed on the mainland. We did not find the species, although few sufficiently moist habitats were searched.

Family TRISSEXODONTIDAE

Oestophora barrelsi Hovestadt & Ripken, 2015

This distinctive endemic was described as a new species from Ilha da Berlenga by HOVESTADT & RIPKEN (2015). These authors pointed out that references to *Caracollina lenticula* and *Oestophora barbula* from the Arquipélago were errors that apparently referred to the new species (see below). This has now been confirmed by checking the older specimens that had been misidentified as *C. lenticula* and by refinding *O. barrelsi* on Farilhão Grande.

Dead and apparently mainly old shells of the species are widespread but rather scarce on exposed soil surfaces on upper parts of Farilhão Grande and commoner in similar situations along the valley in SE. Berlenga Grande from above the harbour and restaurant to beyond the camp-site, and extending sparsely along paths above the NE. shore of the island to opposite Pedra Negra; they apparently do not extend as far south as the lighthouse and they are absent from the SW. of the island. Living snails of this species were found for the first time by GC and again

during the present study, on both islands. These allow more precise description of the habitats in which the species lives, and the first accounts of its body coloration and genital anatomy.

Six living specimens collected on Farilhão Grande were from *ca* 30 m alt. under and amongst gneiss boulders at the base of a small crag, partly shaded near a building and close to the highest point of the island. The living specimens from Berlenga Grande (ten adults, four immatures) were from *ca* 5 m altitude close above the beach at the head of a narrow inlet near the harbour, at the base of a tall steep cliff and well shaded by it for most of the time. They were found on undersides of granite boulders and stones forming part of a scree slope of cliff talus, receiving additional shade from low sprawling trees of *Ficus carica*. There were no associated living molluscs at either locality. Those from Berlenga Grande appeared to be aestivating on 26 July 2018, with a white epiphragm closing the shell mouth.

Bodies of four living snails from Farilhão Grande were all whitish externally, with dorsum and head appearing very pale grey due to sparse and extremely fine dots of blackish pigment; eye spots blackish; ommatophore retractor muscles appearing light grey through the translucent skin. Extracted bodies of specimens fixed in IMS had the mantle-collar whitish; dorsal parts of mantle with pale grey cast due to minute blackish dots; the dots mainly evenly spread, but an unpigmented longitudinal line present with denser concentration of dots along its margins; digestive gland very pale brown. Living specimens from Berlenga Grande had the same pattern of body coloration, but the grey areas were often somewhat darker, light grey rather than pale grey, and some individuals had a light grey streak extending backwards along the right-hand side of forepart of body. The digestive gland was sometimes also darker, light brown rather than pale brown.

Based on the small samples available, shells of the mature living specimens from Berlenga Grande were distinctly darker brown than those from Farilhão Grande. Shell size may be slightly smaller on average on Berlenga Grande, but the ranges overlapped widely: maximum diameter of mature shells (those having thickened peristome) being 8.12-9.69 mm on Berlenga Grande ($n = 56+$), 8.60-10.37 mm on Farilhão Grande ($n = 10$). There were no obvious differences between samples from each island in shell shape, aperture shape, or ribbing.

Anatomy of the distal genitalia was studied in two mature specimens from each island that had been fixed in IMS (Fig. 3). Procedures adopted and equipment used followed those described by HOLYOAK & HOLYOAK (2012: 16) for studies of *Oestophora barbula* and *O. barbellata* (Servain, 1880). The genitalia that were drawn were removed from the bodies. The following anatomical features not shown in the drawings were found to be the same as in those of *O. barbula* and *O. barbellata*: genital pore located low on front of right-hand side of body beneath base of right ommatophore; right ommatophore retractor muscle passes through penial/vaginal angle; penial retractor muscle long and slender, passing proximally alongside columellar muscle, but eventually joined to the diaphragm or sometimes to thin tissue near the spermoviduct in different individuals.

The basic pattern of the distal genitalia of *O. barreli* is clearly that of the genus *Oestophora* Hesse, 1907, with a large accessory sac on the vagina ("vaginal stimulator"), three long mucous glands arising from the vagina and a long penis with a distinct epiphallus (cf. PUENTE, 1996; SCHILEYKO, 2005: 1916). In detail the genitalia of *O. barreli* in fact closely match only those of *O. barbula* s.s., although they are smaller corresponding to its usually smaller body size. HOLYOAK & HOLYOAK (2012: 21, fig 2) showed that *O. barbula* s.s. mostly has its penial epiphallus wider than the penis and

Table III. Uncorrected average *p*-distances of *COI* (below) and 16S rRNA (above) between *Oestophora* species.Table III. Medias sin corrección de *p*-distancias de *COI* (abajo) y 16S rARN (arriba) entre especies de *Oestophora*.

	<i>O. calpeana</i>	<i>O. prietoi</i>	<i>O. mariae</i>	<i>O. ebria</i>	<i>O. ortizi</i>	<i>O. tarnieri</i>	<i>O. silvae</i>	<i>O. barbella</i>	<i>O. barbula</i>	<i>O. barrelsi</i>
<i>O. calpeana</i>		4.3%	8.8%	8.4%	9.1%	9.1%	15.0%	14.9%	15.7%	14.1%
<i>O. prietoi</i>	12.2%		6.8%	7.8%	9.6%	9.6%	12.7%	12.9%	13.1%	13.4%
<i>O. mariae</i>	14.6%	16.0%		8.3%	10.3%	10.3%	13.6%	15.6%	16.3%	14.3%
<i>O. ebria</i>	9.5%	12.5%	13.3%		11.4%	11.6%	15.9%	14.7%	15.4%	13.9%
<i>O. ortizi</i>	11.7%	12.2%	15.3%	10.8%		0.3%	16.7%	13.2%	13.3%	12.8%
<i>O. tarnieri</i>	11.6%	12.1%	15.2%	10.6%	0.2%		16.7%	13.5%	13.6%	13.1%
<i>O. silvae</i>	17.0%	17.2%	17.6%	14.1%	15.3%	15.2%		17.2%	17.4%	17.9%
<i>O. barbella</i>	15.6%	16.1%	16.3%	15.1%	15.2%	15.2%	17.4%		4.5%	8.8%
<i>O. barbula</i>	15.0%	16.7%	16.4%	14.5%	15.6%	15.6%	17.1%	11.2%		9.4%
<i>O. barrelsi</i>	15.5%	16.1%	17.4%	14.2%	14.4%	14.4%	16.4%	13.6%	12.9%	

almost as long, whereas the very similar *O. barbella* has the epiphallus usually thinner than the penis (sometimes equal to it in width) and always much shorter, typically less than half penis length. The relative sizes of penis and epiphallus in *O. barbella* resemble those in all other *Oestophora* species for which the anatomy has been described (e.g. PUENTE, 1996). Thus, *O. barbula* s.s. and *O. barrelsi* resemble each other in penis and epiphallus form and stand apart from all other species of the genus.

Since *O. barbula* s.s. is also the species from the Iberian mainland with most of its geographical range closest to the Arquipélago das Berlengas, it seems very likely to be its closest relative. Although superficially rather different in adult shell size, there is actually complete overlap (maximum breadth in *O. barbula* s.s. 7.5-13.7 mm in large samples: HOLYOAK & HOLYOAK, 2012: 22, table II; compared to 8.1-10.4 mm in 66+ *O. barrelsi*, see above). In fact, the only really diagnostic shell difference is the presence of two strong teeth on the lower lip of the peristome in *O. barbula* s.s., whereas *O. barrelsi* lacks any trace of these. The sharp peripheral keel of the shell of *O. barbula* s.s. is also present in *O. barrelsi*. There are some other shell differences, including proportionately

larger umbilicus in *O. barrelsi*, somewhat lower spire and weaker ribbing, but these features seem rather trivial.

The alternative possibility that *O. barrelsi* is related to one or another of several small-shelled species of *Oestophora* from Andalucía with keeled shells lacking apertural teeth (cf. CADEVALL & OROZCO, 2016: 519-528) appears to be discounted because those Andalusian species with known genital anatomy possess a relatively small penial epiphallus (PUENTE, 1996: 95, 97, 98; pers. obs. by DTH).

Phylogenetic relationships of *Oestophora barrelsi* and other species of the genus based on Bayesian Inference are shown in Fig. 4. The phylogeny presented there was obtained for the combined dataset comprising *COI*, 16SrRNA, and ITS1-5.8S-ITS2-28S. Both Bayesian inference and maximum-likelihood analyses recovered *O. barrelsi* as an independent lineage with full support, having *O. barbula* and *O. barbella* as sister taxa. Those three species joined together as a monophyletic group which was well differentiated from the rest of the Iberian *Oestophora* species.

Average *p*-distances between *Oestophora* species are shown in Table III. Interspecific *p*-distances (excluding values obtained between *O. tarnieri* and *O. ortizi*) ranged from 9.5 % to 17.6% for

Figure 3. Genital anatomy of *Oestophora barrelsi* from Arquipélago das Berlengas. A, B: view from opposite sides of same specimen from Berlenga Grande, 26 July 2018, CGAH site P471; C, D: view from opposite sides of same specimen from Farilhão Grande, 16 May 2018, CGAH site P455. In drawing A the penis was slightly stretched when the specimen was held by pins, when relaxed its penis was of same length as epiphallus. Abbreviations: a: atrium; ag: albumen gland; as: accessory sac on vagina; bc: bursa copulatrix; bcd: duct of bursa copulatrix; e: epiphallus; mg: mucous gland; p: penis; pr: penis retractor muscle; s: spermoviduct; v: vagina; vd: vas deferens.

Figura 3. Anatomía genital de Oestophora barrelsi del Arquipélago das Berlengas. A, B: vista desde lados opuestos del mismo espécimen de Berlenga Grande, 26 de julio de 2018, CGAH estación P471; C, D: vista desde lados opuestos del mismo espécimen de Farilhão Grande, 16 de mayo de 2018, CGAH estación P455. En el dibujo A, el pene estaba ligeramente estirado mientras el espécimen se sujetaba con alfileres, cuando estaba relajado, su pene tenía la misma longitud que el epifalo. Abreviaturas: a: atrio; ag: glándula del albúmen; as: saco accesorio en la vagina; bc: bursa copulatrix; bcd: conducto de la bursa copulatrix; e: epifalo; mg: glándula mucosa; p: pene; pr: músculo retractor del pene; s: espermoviducto; v: vagina; vd: vaso deferente.

COI and, from 4.3% to 17.9% for 16S rRNA.

The DNA sequence data show that *O. barrelsi* diverged from the proto-*O. barbula*+*O. barbella*, and after that separation, *O. barbula* and *O. barbella* diverged from their common ancestor. This evidence of close relationship of the three species supports the recent taxonomic revisions of *Oestophora* which regard *O. barbula* s.l. as closely allied to other species of the genus which lack apertural teeth (PUENTE, 1996; GOMEZ-MOLINER ET AL., 2012).

ALPHABETICAL LIST OF ADDITIONAL SPECIES WITH ERRONEOUS REPORTS FROM THE ARQUIPÉLAGO DAS BERLENGAS

Candidula unifasciata (Poiret, 1801) - Two samples in the Matos Collection at MCUC (2019.17.00325, 00347) from "Berlenga" (= Berlenga Grande) labelled as this species were reidentified by us as shells of the *Xeroplexa olisippensis* s.l. that is abundant on the island (see above). MATOS (2014: 204-205) reported and mapped a few localities in Portugal, but not her own from Berlenga. HOLYOAK ET AL. (2019: 151) reidentified her figura 166 (from Coimbra) as *Xeroplexa* cf. *olisippensis* and figura 167 (of "*Helicella rugosiuscula* Michaud" from Barreiro) as either *Microxeromagna lowei* (Potiez & Michaud, 1838) or *Xerotricha conspurcata*. CADEVALL & OROZCO (2016: 715) did not accept any Iberian records of *C. unifasciata*, although it possibly occurs in the Pyrenees, since it is widespread on the French side.

Caracollina lenticula (A. Férussac, 1821) - MATOS (2014: 179, fig. 43, lower shell) erroneously figured a specimen of the then undescribed *Oestophora barrelsi* (see above) as *Caracollina lenticula* from Farilhão Grande. Records from "Ilha Berlenga como no Farilhão" in her account of *C. lenticula* on the following page and on the accompanying map (p. 180) were therefore presumably based on *O. barrelsi*. This receives direct confirmation from specimens we reidentified

as *O. barrelsi* that were labelled as *Caracollina lenticula* in the Matos Collection at MCUC: five samples from Berlenga (2019.17.00303, 00324, 00338, 00351, 00357) and four from Farilhões (2019.17.00313, 00352, 00356, 00379).

Cernuella virgata (Da Costa, 1778) - Two specimens labelled as this species in the Matos Collection at MCUC are unconvincing. Each of them consists of a single shell. 2019.17.00036, Berlenga W do Faro, 19 June 1996 is an adult shell with no colour remaining; 2019.17.00408, Berlenga, Planalto da Cisterna, 9 June 1994, HF, is a rather old adult shell, which might be a worn shell of *Xeroplexa*. Even if the identification is correct, it is possible that these single shells could have reached the island in the digestive tracts of Yellow-legged Gulls which had fed on the adjacent mainland of Portugal where *C. virgata* is common.

Cochlicella barbara (Linnaeus, 1758) - Five samples labelled as *C. barbara* from Berlenga Grande in the Matos Collection at MCUC comprise three samples we have reidentified as *C. conoidea* (2019.17.00310, 7 sh; 2019.17.00327, sh unusually tall for *C. conoidea*; 2019.17.00395, 4 in alcohol) and two samples of shells so immature that identification to species level would be unreliable (2019.17.00311; 2019.17.00376). CADEVALL & OROZCO (2016: 371) suggested that juvenile shells of *C. barbara* possess spiral striae on the protoconch ("estriaciones espirales, en el mismo sentido que las vueltas") which serve to differentiate it from other species of the genus. However, Iberian material in CGAH shows the striae are often lacking or almost invisible in *C. barbara*, while *C. acuta* sometimes has weak spiral striae on its upper whorls.

Helicella cistorum (Morelet, 1845) - Treatment of this species by MATOS (2014: 193-194) was confused by misidentifications. Her fig. 155 (Serra da Arrábida) represents *Xeroplexa arrabidensis* G. Holyoak & D. Holyoak, 2014; fig. 156 (Berlenga = Berlenga Grande) represents a *Xeroplexa* species, resembling *X. olisippensis* (see above); fig. 157 ("Loulé,

Figure 4. Phylogenetic relationships of *Oestophora* based on Bayesian Inference from the combined dataset of two mitochondrial gene fragments (COI and 16S rRNA) and one nuclear gene cluster (ITS1-5.8S rRNA-ITS2-28S rRNA). Numbers at nodes correspond to Bayesian posterior probabilities (above) and maximum-likelihood bootstrap support values (below).

Figura 4. Relaciones filogenéticas entre especies de *Oestophora* basadas en el análisis de inferencia bayesiana para el conjunto de datos de dos fragmentos mitocondriales (COI y 16S rRNA) y un gen nuclear (ITS1-5.8S rRNA-ITS2-28S rRNA). Los números junto a los nodos indican la probabilidad posterior bayesiana (arriba) y los valores de soporte “bootstrap” para el análisis de máxima verosimilitud (abajo).

como *Helicella stiparum*”) represents *X. scabiosula* Locard, 1899; the dot on Mapa 106 for the Farilhões also represents *Xeroplexa* sp. (the only Geomitridae sp. known there other than *Cochlicella acuta*). Our records of *H. cistorum* in Portugal have been checked anatomically to demonstrate the paired dart sacs of *Helicella* rather than the single dart sac of *Xeroplexa*. They were reported by HOLYOAK, HOLYOAK & MENDES (2014:

49-50) as extending from a wide scatter in the Algarve northwards through Alentejo to much of eastern Beira Baixa; HOLYOAK ET AL. (2019: 141) added finds much further north in Trás-os-Montes e Alto Douro. Hence *H. cistorum* remains unknown in Estremadura and Beira Litoral and has an overall range that does not reach the western Atlantic coast of the country. All material we have dissected from Berlenga Grande

and Farilhão Grande shows the single dart sac of *Xeroplexa*. Samples from the Arquipélago in the Matos Collection at MCUC labelled as *Helicella cistorum* show the shell characters of the *Xeroplexa olisippensis* s.l. morphotypes on each of the islands, with no hint that *H. cistorum* is involved. Two such samples are from Berlenga (= Berlenga Grande) (2019.17.00312, 00388), four samples from Farilhão Grande (2019.17. 00358, 00366, 00367, 00387), and one lacks a locality (2019.17.00377).

Oestophora barbula (Rossmässler, 1838) - Reported as *Helix barbula* from Farilhão Grande by GIRARD (in DAVEAU, 1884: 446) based on collections by Jules Daveau. Since he noted that the shell was nearly adult, rolled, and possessed no apertural teeth it is clear that this record can now be referred to *O. barreli* (see above). NOBRE (in NOBRE & BRAGA (1942: 11) reported *O. barbula* from Berlenga Grande, and NOBRE (1941: 87) "Berlengas (N.)", where N. presumably represented Nobre's own record. Since there have been no subsequent confirmed records of *O. barbula* from the island whereas *O. barreli* shells are abundant near the harbour and along the valley above it there seems little doubt that an error was involved.

Xeroplexa intersecta (Poiret, 1801) - The Matos Collection at MCUC contains five samples of shells from Farilhão Grande labelled as this species (2019.17.00331, 00363, 00364, 00369) which we have reidentified as the distinctive *Xeroplexa* shell form on this island (see above) They show its characteristic large shell size in which a peripheral keel persists when adult. Our dissections reveal this population has a long penial flagellum as e.g. in *X. olisippensis*. The Matos Collection at MCUC also contains one sample from Berlenga (= Berlenga Grande) labelled as *Candidula intersecta* (2019.17.00334) but reidentified by us as shells of the characteristic form for the *Xeroplexa* from that island (cf. Fig. 2A-C), which again has a long penial flagellum as e.g. in *X. olisippensis*. *Candidula intersecta* (Poiret, 1801), with identification characters (normally

including a short penial flagellum) and Portuguese records reviewed by HOLYOAK & HOLYOAK (2014: 644-646), was transferred to *Xeroplexa* by CHUECA ET AL. (2018: 366). The latter authors found two clades among material from N. Spain, that from Galicia apparently being localised with a long penial flagellum, that from the Basque country extending to NW. Europe and having a short penial flagellum. The Portuguese mainland specimens also have a short flagellum and study of these is being continued by L.J. Chueca.

Xerosecta promissa (Westerlund, 1893) - Three shells from Berlenga in the Matos Collection labelled as "*Xerosecta promissa*?" (MCUC 2019.17.00374) apparently represent *Xeroplexa* from this island. MATOS (2014: 212-213) gave a few Portuguese records of *X. promissa* but did not mention her own possible record from Berlenga.

Xerotricha conspurcata (Draparnaud, 1801) - NOBRE (1941: 102) reported this species from both Berlenga and Farilhão with an indication these were his own records. However, NOBRE (in NOBRE & BRAGA (1942) did not mention it. MATOS (2002: 35, fig. 15) reported it from Berlenga Grande ("proximidades da Cisterna e no trilho até à Fortaleza, onde só observámos cinco vivos"), but not Farilhão Grande ("Não foi encontrada"). MATOS (2014: 190) also mapped it for Berlenga Grande (recent record) and Farilhão Grande (as old record). Study of the Matos Collection at MCUC revealed that all eight of her samples from Berlenga Grande are comprised of immature shells of the local *Xeroplexa* (samples 2019.17.00302, 00316, 00343, 00346, 00355, 00375, 00380, 00391; 50+ sh in total). We did not see it.

CONCLUSIONS

Only two land snail taxa (now identified as *Xeroplexa olisippensis* s.l. and *Oestophora barreli*) were reported as collected on Farilhão Grande in 1883 by Jules Daveau (GIRARD in DAVEAU, 1884: 446-447). MATOS (2002) found just three

(adding *Cochlicella acuta*); all of the latter author's material from the island lodged in her collection at MCUC has been reassessed by us. Our own results from 16 May 2018 were based on prolonged searches by four malacologists, which produced just the two species recorded by Girard. We were able to search all readily accessible places high on the island and along the steep path up its southern slopes, in good weather conditions, on a small islet that has suffered little disturbance. Both species recorded by us were found repeatedly, with *Xeroplexa* in large numbers, and both occurred in each of the two hectads of the MGRS grid (29SMD56, and the small part of 29SMD57 forming the northern part of the islet).

NOBRE (in NOBRE & BRAGA, 1942: 10-11) gave a strange list of just three species for Farilhão Grande, comprising *Lauria cylindracea* (as *Pupa umbilicata*), *Cochlicella acuta* (as *Helix barbara*) and *Theba pisana* (as *Helix pisana*), all three being marked "N." which was how this author denoted his own records. Furthermore, all three species he listed were previously unrecorded on the island and only one of them (*C. acuta*) has been found there subsequently. It also seems implausible that in the 1940s Nobre should have failed to find the *Xeroplexa* and *Oestophora* recorded consistently by other visitors searching earlier (1883) and later (1996, 2018), especially since both were very easy to find in 2018. Hence, we reject all of Nobre's list for Farilhão Grande, despite acceptance of these records by MATOS (2002, 2014), and all of the species involved being known from Berlenga Grande and common on the Portuguese coast. Thus, we present the list for Farilhão Grande as consisting only of the three species for which we have confirmed specimens of sound provenance.

For Berlenga Grande we accept records of 14 species (discounting *Cornu aspersum* because there is no evidence it ever formed an established population), two of which are newly reported in this paper. Whether the *Xeroplexa* on Berlenga Grande is eventually regarded as

a single-island endemic species or subspecies is a matter still to be decided by ongoing research, since its apparent distinction from populations in mainland Portugal based on mitochondrial DNA data does not appear to be accompanied by any clear differences from them in shell characters or genital anatomy.

The total number of land-snail species with confirmed records for Arquipélago das Berlengas as a whole is thus 14. *Oestophora barrelsi* is the only endemic species, occurring on both islands of the archipelago. All records of nine other species, two based only on bibliographic records and seven others based on MCUC museum specimens, are dismissed as due to misidentifications.

This study provides a clear demonstration of the value of a comprehensive and numerous set of voucher specimens. The detailed inventory and well curated Matos Collection now housed and accessible at MCUC has allowed distinction between past misidentifications, name changes due to the needs for revision and updating of taxonomy or nomenclature, and the more interesting genuine historic changes in the fauna of the Arquipélago. Assessment of historic changes between the faunas in the 1880s, 1940s and more recent times rely largely on old literature, since the specimens have all or mostly been lost. However, comparison of records from 1994-1996 with those from 2018-2019 have been checked directly from the voucher specimens. Hence, it is apparent that on Berlenga Grande, *Xerotricha apicina* regarded as plentiful in the 1880s was scarce in the 1990s and it may have gone by 2018. On the other hand, *Otala lactea* has been recorded as a relatively recent arrival that may already be rare, and *Cochlicella acuta* and *Portugala inchoata* may no longer occur on the island.

Truncatellina callicratis and *Vitrea contracta* were both discovered new to this island in 2018-2019. Their very small shells may have been overlooked in the past when researchers did not use sieving techniques and probably did not collect soil samples for detailed scrutiny. However, although both were found in

large numbers in 2019 the records were from the area beside the camping ground, where accidental introductions seem quite likely. Indeed, the long history of human occupation on Berlenga Grande and of import of building materials, etc., from the mainland makes it probable that other land snail species arrived as introductions. There is direct evidence that *Otala lactea* arrived as human food, and the same is possible for *Theba p. pisana*.

Nevertheless, it has been realised rather belatedly that the Arquipélago supports the endemic species *Oestophora barreysi*, which seems to have been derived from the related *O. barbula s.s.* living on the adjacent mainland of Portugal. The contemporary sea gap between the Arquipélago and the mainland is over 10 km wide. Nevertheless, it is unclear whether isolation from mainland populations was involved in differentiation of *O. barreysi*, since the intervening water depths are of more than 20 metres but less than 40 metres. The history of global sea-level changes during the Pleistocene is now well documented (e.g. PILLANS, CHAPPELL & NAISH, 1998; BINTANJA, VAN DE WAL & OERLEMANS, 2005), and this implies that such depths would have resulted in recurrence of land connections between Berlenga and the mainland during cold stages of the Pleistocene. It nonetheless remains possible that *O. barreysi* differentiated as an island population while isolated during the high sea stand of a Pleistocene warm stage, or that unsuitable habitats on what is now the intervening sea-bed prevented colonisation even when land bridges did exist.

Isolation might also have been involved in development of the conspicuously different morphotypes of *Xeroplexa olisippensis s.l.* on Berlenga Grande and Farilhão Grande, which are ca 7 km apart. This wide separation of the islands perhaps also makes it rather surprising that *Oestophora barreysi* is present on both islands and has been known on both since the 1880s. Its shells from Farilhão Grande are slightly smaller and paler than those from Berlenga Grande,

and the exposed parts of their bodies are somewhat lighter grey dorsally, but the differences involved seem slight and the DNA sequence data (Fig. 4) show no differences. Hence, it seems possible that the population on Farilhão Grande was an early anthropogenic introduction, perhaps with construction materials. We found it living there only in small numbers and only beside a wall adjoining the (relatively modern) lighthouse at the summit of the island.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We are grateful to Ana Catarina Ambrosina da Silva and José Mendes Simões for assistance in collecting specimens during our fieldwork. Thanks are also due to the diving centres Haliotis and JustDive for transport to Farilhão Grande. Field work was done under the permit 11036/2018/DCNF-LVT/DLAP. The Rangers provided assistance on Berlenga Grande. Our visit to study specimens in the collection of the late R.M. Albuquerque de Matos at the Museu da Ciência, Universidade de Coimbra, Portugal was greatly assisted by Dr André Breves Ramos. Hence this paper benefited from the use of the Portuguese Infrastructure for Scientific Collections (PRISC.pt). Prior careful curatorial work on the Matos Collection and preparation of an inventory of its specimens by Ana Catarina Ambrosina da Silva (former undergraduate biology student at Lusófona University) also facilitated our study. LJC was supported by a Post-doctoral Fellowship awarded by the Department of Education, Universities and Research of the Basque Government (Ref.: POS_2018_1_0012). The authors / G.C. acknowledge FCT - Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (Portugal), through the strategic project UIDB/04292/2020 granted to MARE. We thank Dr Amaia Caro for help with DNA isolation and sequencing and we are also very grateful to Prof. Benjamin Gómez Moliner and Dr Carlos Prieto for helpful comments on a draft of this paper.

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